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An Assessment Of Factors Influencing The Development Of Small And Medium Enterprise In Bayelsa State

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ABSTRACT

The study looked at the assessment of factors influencing the development of small and medium enterprise in Bayelsa State. The study used the descriptive survey research design. The population consists of two hundred and thirty (230) entrepreneurs from various firms in Bayelsa State. The entire population was adopted as sample for the study. The study developed an instrument titled “Assessment of Factors Influencing the Development of Small and Medium Enterprise” (AFIDSME). The instrument is a four point rating scale consisting of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The response options were weighed as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was subjected to face validation by an expert in the department of business Administration in Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State. The validator checked the language content of the instrument and made appropriate corrections before final copy was sent to the field to respondents. The data obtained from the study was analyzed using simple mean. Findings accrued from research question 1, table 1 showed that item 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 opinion of respondents were all accepted and they had a mean value of 3.33, 3.44, 3.56, 3.78, 3.23 and 3.56 respectively. This implies that financial constraints, Poor management skills, lack of training and experience, poor infrastructure, insufficient profits and low demand for products and services hinders the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State. Findings accrued from research question 2, table 2 showed that items 7, 8, 9 and 10 responses were all accepted and had a mean value of 3.44, 3.56, 3.25 and 3.88 respectively. This implies that government policy on interest rates raises cost of doing business, bad government credit laws, bad implementation of government tax laws and government licensing regulations. Findings accrued from research question 3, table 3 showed that items 11, 12, 13 and 14 responses were all accepted and had a mean value of 3.55, 3.67, 3.78 and 3.12 respectively. This implies that the decline of SMEs business would cause inflation and hinders economic growth, low SMEs industries reduces the supply of goods and services; the decline of SMEs reduces the internally generated revenue of the state and the decline of SMEs increases unemployment rate in Bayelsa State. Based on the findings obtained from the study, it was recommended that government should strengthen its policy to encourage the growth of SMEs in the state. Also, government should provide soft loans to business owners to expand the growth of their business.

Keywords: Assessment, Factors, Influencing, Development, Small, Medium and Enterprise

INTRODUCTION

The concept performance is open to wide variations in meaning as it is a somewhat indefinite word when it is used in research. The lack of consensus on the meaning generates misperception and obviously limits

the potential for review and comparability of studies in the area. For instance, performance management, firm performance, performance measurement, performance assessment or performance evaluations are used interchangeably. The dictionary of management sciences defines performance as the accomplishment of a given task measured against pre-set known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed (Al-Dhaafri, Al-Swidi, & Yusuff, 2016; Sorooshian et al., 2016). Accordingly, to perfectly evaluate how well an organization is performing, there is a need to develop some assessable measures. This can be attained by recognizing those aspects of the business procedures that need modification for improvement and those that are working well (Aminu & Mahmood, 2016). The firm's productivity for a certain period of time can be measured by this process and accurate result or output compared with actual inputs determines the performance of a firm (Al-Dhaafri et al., Shehu & Mahmood, 2014). SME performance can be measured by using different criteria or indicators such as financial and non-financial measures. Financially, it can be measured by looking at return on investment, profitability, return on assets, market share and sales growth among others while non-financial measures will look at competitiveness, employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction, service quality and innovation among others. An SME is said to be performing when it achieves its overall objectives with effective and efficient utilization of its resources (Aminu & Mahmood, 2016; Semrau, Ambos, & Kraus, 2016). Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria have not performed creditably well and hence have not played the expected vital and vibrant role in the economic growth and development of Nigeria. This situation has been of great concern to the government, citizenry, operators, practitioners and the organized private sector groups. Year in year out, the governments at federal, state and even local levels through budgetary allocations, policies and pronouncements have signified interest and acknowledgement of the crucial role of the SME sub-sector of the economy and hence made policies for energizing the same. There have also been fiscal incentives, grants, bilateral and multilateral agencies support and aids as well as specialized institutions all geared towards making the SME sub-sector vibrant. Just as it has been a great concern to all and sundry to promote the welfare of SMEs, it has also been a great cause of concern to all, the fact that the vital sub-sector has fallen short of expectation. The situation is more disturbing and worrying when compared with what other developing and developed countries have been able to achieve with their SMEs. It has been shown that there is a high correlation between the degree of poverty hunger, unemployment, economic well-being (standard of living) of the citizens of countries and the degree of vibrancy of the respective country's SMEs. If Nigeria were to achieve an appreciable success towards attaining the Millennium Declaration Goals for 2015, one of the sure ways would be to vigorously pursue the development of its SMEs. Some of the key Millennium Declaration Goals like halving the proportion of people living in extreme poverty, suffering from hunger, without access to safe water, reducing maternal and infant mortality by three-quarters and two thirds respectively and enrolment of all children in primary school by 2015 may indeed be a mirage unless there is a turnaround of our SMEs' fortunes sooner than later. The time is now to do something surgical to the situation of our SMEs given the aggravating level of poverty in Nigeria and the need to meet up with the Millennium Declaration Goals.

Statement of Problem

The sharp decline and closure of small and medium enterprise outfit in the state is alarming. Observation show that most businesses are closing down mainly as a result of low patronage and government policies. There is the need to assess factors influencing the development of small and medium enterprise in Bayelsa State.

Dr. Ade Oyedijo, a financial expert in a paper titled "Nigeria's Economy and its Career Promise for the Mature Employee" affirmed that the plights of SMEs in Nigeria have to do with key variables and challenges that characterize the nation's economy. These include but are not limited to a very high unemployment rate, which is expected to increase as a result of the current ongoing public sector reforms, high unemployment rate, high poverty level, disease, hunger, etc. Dr. Oyedijo also mentioned a drastic shift from the production of non-oil traded goods (mostly agricultural) to traded goods while about 95 million Nigerians are reported to be living below the poverty line even as 19 of her citizens are ranked among the 500 wealthiest men in modern capitalist economy as among the characteristics of our nation's economy which aggravate the problems of Nigerian SMEs. He also opined that since independence, the

main thrust of Nigeria's development strategies and objectives have been the development of industrialization, education and a self-reliant economy but regretted that the human capital which is expected to support the industrialization process and propel other sectors to maturity has not exhibited the right mix of knowledge, attitude and skills required to achieve this purpose.

Purpose of the Study

The broad aim of this study is to:

1. Find out factors hindering the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State.
2. Find out the influence of government policies on the growth of SME in Bayelsa State.
3. Determine the economic impact of decline of SMEs in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the factors hindering the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State?
2. What is the influence of government policies on the growth of SME in Bayelsa State?
3. What is the economic impact of decline of SMEs in Bayelsa State?

Scope of the Study

The study is limited to the assessment of factors influencing the development of small and medium enterprise in Bayelsa State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the years, SMEs appears to have attracted increasing attention from researchers. However, studies on SME performance in emerging economies are still relatively limited in terms of their scope and focus (Aminu & Shariff, 2015). For example, studies by Alegre and Chiva (2013), Chen, Jaw, and Wu (2016), Deshpande, Grinstein, Snow, and Elie (2013), Kreiser, Marino, Kuratko, and Weaver (2013) and Lechner and Gudmundsson (2012) have all contributed in investigating SMEs performance but mostly in developed countries as SMEs are key contributors to the various nation's GDP. Conversely, there are a number of studies on SMEs performance in emerging markets that investigated the role of strategic orientations towards SMEs performance (Al-Dhaafri et al., 2016; Aminu & Shariff, 2015; Chen et al., 2016; Matchaba-hove, Farrington, & Sharp, 2015; Semrau et al., 2016). As suggested by Aminu (2015) and Adeniyi (2011), there is still room for further investigation on the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation, technology orientation, contemporary marketing and SME's performance in an emerging economy like Nigeria.

The main objective of the study is to analyze some determinants of SME performance and find out whether government support has a moderating role in that relationship. To achieve this, resource-based view theory, as firms' internal resources, was applied as underpinning theory to determine the competitive advantages. Validity and reliability are the two frequently encountered concepts in the measurement and evaluation of constructs and are important for defining and measuring bias and distortion. As such, establishing the validity and reliability of the survey instrument is essential before it can be used in the study so as to be free from bias and distortion. According to Hair, Hult, Ringle and Sarstedt (2014) and Sekaran and Bougie (2013), validity refers to the effect of an instrument in measuring the construct it is designed to measure and determines whether the research truly measures what it was intended to measure, while reliability is the level of internal consistency or stability of the measuring device over time. In other words, it is the consistency of an instrument to produce the same results each time it was used (Urban & Barreria, 2010).

A dynamic SME sub-sector is vital and imperative for the overall economic development of the country. Aside from providing opportunities for employment generation, SMEs help to provide effective means of curtailing rural-urban migration and resource utilization. By largely producing intermediate products for use in large-scale companies, SMEs contribute to the strengthening of industrial inter-linkages and integration. A vibrant, efficient and effective SME sub-sector generates many resultant benefits for stakeholders, employees, customers, employers as well as the entire economy's benefits. Employees require new skills and knowledge to improve their performance on the job and to compete with their counterparts in other parts of the world. Customers on their part tend to enjoy personalized service and

attention because of the keen competition, focus and innovation, which characterise the operations of SMEs. Employers or rather SME entrepreneurs on the other hand are either motivated or compelled by competition to learn and broaden their knowledge and skills in order to meet up with the challenges of maintaining good relationship with their financiers (banks and other financial institutions), auditors, regulators and even their competitors. They achieve this by belonging to and participating actively in the activities of appropriate chambers of commerce, trade groups, various fora, exhibitions, etc where ideas, new concepts and knowledge are shared and discussed. The bottom line of all these is that the relevant SME would remain efficient and profitable and hence contribute to the growth and development of the entire economy. Many International Development Agencies, organisations, and financiers not only appreciate the great roles played by SMEs in poverty alleviation and overall economic development, but also invest a significant percentage of their resources in them (SMEs). A review of World Bank Operations revealed that it invested a whopping \$1.597 billion in SMEs in 2004 fiscal year, with Africa getting a sizeable share of over \$89 million. This sum was channeled through the four major development arms of the bank: the International Finance Corporation (IFC), the Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency (MIGA), the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD), and the International Development Association (IDA). Nigeria, Kenya and Uganda benefited from part of the new joint pilot programme executed by IFC and IDA for SME development in 2004 to the tune of \$70million. The 2004 annual review of the IFC’s Small Business Activities indicate that the IFC and IDA began SME project development in Nigeria worth \$32 million. In Kenya and Uganda, \$22 million and \$16 million were also respectively invested in similar projects. In recognition of the crucial role SMEs play in economic growth and development, the Bank of Industry generated over sixty percent (60%) of the entire loans it granted in 2004 to SMEs, the relatively high default rate notwithstanding. The Managing Director of the Bank of Industry, Dr. Lawrence Osa-Afiana also confirmed that twenty nine (29) of the 594 loan applications received by the bank since 2001 received approval adding that N20.8 million or 19.1 percent of the total approved loans went to the SME sub-sector. The Bank of Industry is also intensifying efforts to source cheaper funds from Development Financial Institutions (DFIs) such as the African Development Bank (ADB), African Export-Import Bank, European Development Bank, etc so as to on-lend to SMEs at concessionary rates and thus maximize their value addition.

METHODS

The study used the descriptive survey research design. The population consists of two hundred and thirty (230) entrepreneurs from various firms in Bayelsa State. The entire population was adopted as sample for the study. The study developed an instrument titled “Assessment of Factors Influencing the Development of Small and Medium Enterprise” (AFIDSME). The instrument is a four point rating scale consisting of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The response options were weighed as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was subjected to face validation by an expert in the department of business Administration in Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State. The validator checked the language content of the instrument and made appropriate corrections before final copy was sent to the field to respondents. The data obtained from the study was analyzed using simple mean.

DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question 1

What is the factors hindering the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Factors hindering the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State

S/N	Items	Mean	Decision
1	Financial constraints hinders the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State	3.33	Accept
2	Poor management skills hinders the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State	3.44	Accept
3	Lack of training and experience hinders the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State	3.56	Accept
4	Poor infrastructure hinders the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State.	3.78	Accept
5	Insufficient profits hinder the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State.	3.23	Accept
6	Low demand for products and services hinders the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State.	3.56	Accept

Findings accrued from research question 1, table 1 showed that item 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 opinion of respondents were all accepted and they had a mean value of 3.33, 3.44, 3.56, 3.78, 3.23 and 3.56 respectively. This implies that financial constraints, Poor management skills, lack of training and experience, poor infrastructure, insufficient profits and low demand for products and services hinders the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State.

Research Question 2: *What is the influence of government policies on the growth of SME in Bayelsa State?*

Table 2: Influence of Government Policies on the Growth of SME in Bayelsa State

S/N	Items	Mean	Decision
7	Government policy on interest rates raises cost of doing business.	3.44	Accept
8	Bad government credit laws affects the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State	3.56	Accept
9	Bad implementation of government tax laws hinders the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State.	3.25	Accept
10	Government licensing regulations affects the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State.	3.88	Accept

Findings accrued from research question 2, table 2 showed that items 7, 8, 9 and 10 responses were all accepted and had a mean value of 3.44, 3.56, 3.25 and 3.88 respectively. This implies that government policy on interest rates raises cost of doing business, bad government credit laws, bad implementation of government tax laws and government licensing regulations.

Research Question 3

What is the economic impact of decline of SMEs in Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Economic Impact of Decline of SMEs in Bayelsa State

S/N	Items	Mean	Decision
11	The decline of SMEs business would cause inflation and hinders economic growth.	3.55	Accept
12	Low SMEs industries reduces the supply of goods and services	3.67	Accept
13	The decline of SMEs reduces the internally generated revenue of the state.	3.78	Accept
14	The decline of SMEs increases unemployment rate in Bayelsa State.	3.12	Accept

Findings accrued from research question 3, table 3 showed that items 11, 12, 13 and 14 responses were all accepted and had a mean value of 3.55, 3.67, 3.78 and 3.12 respectively. This implies that the decline of SMEs business would cause inflation and hinders economic growth, low SMEs industries reduces the supply of goods and services; the decline of SMEs reduces the internally generated revenue of the state and the decline of SMEs increases unemployment rate in Bayelsa State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings accrued from research question 1, table 1 showed that item 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 opinion of respondents were all accepted and they had a mean value of 3.33, 3.44, 3.56, 3.78, 3.23 and 3.56 respectively. This implies that financial constraints, Poor management skills, lack of training and experience, poor infrastructure, insufficient profits and low demand for products and services hinders the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State. This is in line with the view of Abdul Majid, Kamaludin, Md.Saad, & Aziz, (2012) that states that SMEs can only thrive in an healthy environment where all conditions are conducive.

Findings accrued from research question 2, table 2 showed that items 7, 8, 9 and 10 responses were all accepted and had a mean value of 3.44, 3.56, 3.25 and 3.88 respectively. This implies that government policy on interest rates raises cost of doing business, bad government credit laws, bad implementation of

government tax laws and government licensing regulations. This is also in agreement with the view of Aminu, & Shariff, (2015) that said that government policy and tax may significantly affect the growth of SMEs in a place.

Findings accrued from research question 3, table 3 showed that items 11, 12, 13 and 14 responses were all accepted and had a mean value of 3.55, 3.67, 3.78 and 3.12 respectively. This implies that the decline of SMEs business would cause inflation and hinders economic growth, low SMEs industries reduces the supply of goods and services; the decline of SMEs reduces the internally generated revenue of the state and the decline of SMEs increases unemployment rate in Bayelsa State. Further, Alegre, & Chiva, (2013) opined that the decline in SMEs can cause unemployment and low supply of goods and services.

CONCLUSION

In all, the study showed that financial constraints, Poor management skills, lack of training and experience, poor infrastructure, insufficient profits and low demand for products and services hinders the growth of SMEs in Bayelsa State. Also, the decline of SMEs business would cause inflation and hinders economic growth, low SMEs industries reduces the supply of goods and services; the decline of SMEs reduces the internally generated revenue of the state and the decline of SMEs increases unemployment rate in Bayelsa State. Finally, government policy on interest rates raises cost of doing business, bad government credit laws, bad implementation of government tax laws and government licensing regulations.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings obtained from the study, it was recommended that:

1. Government should strengthen its policy to encourage the growth of SMEs in the state.
2. Government should provide soft loans to business owners to expand the growth of their business.

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